

Minutes of the 47th Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Tuesday 5th July 2011

(This document was finalised on 11th October 2011)

Present:

Dr Bogdan Antonescu⁵ (BA)
Mrs Melanie Collins² (MC)
Mr Owen Cox² (OC)
Dr Catherine Gaffard² (CG)
Dr David Hooper^{3,4} (DAH) Secretary
Dr Dirk Klugmann² (DK)
Mr Chris Lee⁵ (CFL)
Dr Graham Parton^{1,4} (GAP)
Dr Isobel Piper² (IP)
Prof Geraint Vaughan⁵ (GV) Chair
Mr Charles Wrench^{3,4} CLW

¹British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

²Met Office

³NERC MST Radar Facility

⁴Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁵University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

amsl above mean sea level
BL(WP) Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
COST European Cooperation in Science and Technology
DPW Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
ECMWF European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EGN Emily Norton (FGAM instrument scientist)
EUCOS EUMETNET Composite Observing System
FAAM Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
FGAM Facility for Ground based Atmospheric Measurements
GPS Global Positioning System
H&S Health and Safety
ISP Internet Service Provider
LAN Local Area Network
LCBR Laser Cloud Base Recorder
LD Les Dean (part-time MSTRF site technician)
MSE Mesosphere Summer Echo
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
NLC Noctilucent Cloud
PC Personal Computer
UT Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

GV pointed out that the reference to a “*water vapour lidar*” in the following sentence from the first paragraph of section 6e on page 10 - “*A Raman lidar could be used during the daytime, but a water vapour lidar would be far more appropriate.*” - should have been to a “*DIAL water vapour lidar*”

The minutes of the 46th meeting were otherwise accepted as being correct.

2. Matters arising

GV enquired about the outcome of the tests for a potential secondary LOFAR receiving station in the Aberystwyth area - section 3a on page 2. DAH reported that a local mobile phone transmitter had proved to be a far-more significant source of VHF “noise” than the MST radar.

ACTION ITEM 44.4.2 DAH and GAP to ensure that different versions of MST radar data products stored on the BADC are clearly distinguishable and that no old versions are deleted when the reprocessing of the entire observation archive is undertaken.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that although no new versions of MST radar data products have yet been created, a new BADC data management plan which addresses the above issues is now in place. GAP will report on this in section 3d. DAH will delay reprocessing the entire observation archive until he has modified the version 3 signal processing software to make use of updated Python programming libraries. At present the software can only be run on his old PC, which is too slow to make large-scale reprocessing practical. However, he is happy to reprocess individual days on request. GV emphasised the scientific importance of having homogeneous data products available for the entire archive. He therefore urged DAH to assign a high priority to this task.

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 46.4.1 DK to set up a working group for developing quality control algorithms for wind-profiling radars.

ONGOING

DK has recently visited Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), who are also very interested in the above issue. One idea is to set up the working group under the wider auspices of the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) Global Reference Upper Air Network (GRUAN). Within the Met Office, CG has already started to look into the fine details of wind-profiler (WP) model comparison statistics - see section 6e. MC, who already has experience of AMDAR and other upper air data, will start to become more involved with WP work.

ACTION ITEM 46.5.1 EGN to send DK a copy of the report on the potential impact of Galileo operations on BLWPs.

COMPLETED

DK reported that the main person responsible for frequency allocation issues within the Met Office has been heavily involved in trying to protect boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) operations within the 1290 MHz band. The Met Office commissioned an independent study on the future of BLWP operations from the University of Bath. It concluded that that 1290 MHz band should continue to be used on this basis that: it is the one which is most-widely used for BLWP operations throughout Europe; it is the one which is best-protected for such use within the UK. Tim Oakley will coordinate action on this issue within the EUMETNET framework. EGN had also sent DK details of the threats to BLWP operations caused by wind turbines. The contamination of the radar returns by turbine echoes is becoming an increasing problem and necessitates the use of improved clutter screen designs.

ACTION ITEM 46.5.2 DAH and DK to investigate the possibility of operating one of the Met Office's new Jenoptik LCBRs at the MSTRF site.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that DK and IP had visited the radar site on 7th April 2011 in connection with this action. He added that Dave Wareing (DPW) had subsequently created a conduit for routing cables underneath the paving slabs between the site bungalow and the instrument compound, where the LCBR would be located. DK stated that, for reasons of Met Office security, it would probably be necessary to have a dedicated local area network (LAN) and broadband connection for the new instrument. DAH confirmed that there was still one telephone line available (the one used for the fire alarm system) which is not already used for broadband. DK still needs to make a case, within the Met Office, for siting one of the new instruments at Aberystwyth rather than at Aberporth. He is keen to have one in operation alongside a WP. It may be that the only way to achieve this is to use one of the older Jenoptik instruments for the MST radar site. However, since the Met Office are experiencing some minor problems with the newer model, such an arrangement would not be disadvantageous.

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik LCBRs on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that the BADC are now ready to receive the new files. OC will start to make the data available once he has ensured that the files are compliant with the Climate and Forecasts (CF) meta-data standards. DK added that it is still necessary to establish the exact interpretation of the backscatter signal strength parameter. It appears to relate to the signal-to-noise ratio, although this is not the most scientifically-useful parameter. It would be much better to have access to the raw photon counts per shot. OC is following up this issue with the manufacturers.

ACTION ITEM 46.6.1 DK to set up a working group for those with expertise in lidar operations.

ONGOING

DK reported that for the purposes of numerical weather prediction, boundary-layer (BL) temperature and humidity are two of the most important parameters. At present these are only available from AM-DAR (i.e. aircraft) and from radiosondes. DK would eventually like to have an operational lidar system for measuring at least the BL humidity. However, he does not expect this to be achieved in the short

term. He is keen to investigate all potential technical solutions and to collaborate with any groups, including the University of Manchester, who have the appropriate expertise. In a collaboration with CLW and Judith Agnew, he has already been investigating the possibility of buying a low-power laser to test on the existing Chilbolton system. The hope is that such a laser might operate more reliably than the existing one but still produce enough power to cover the BL.

3. Facility Report - DAH

3a) MST Radar renovation

The primary focus of the renovation work was on replacing the radar's beam steering components. These had been repeatedly reconditioned over the course of 20 years, albeit with diminishing returns in recent years. The poor state of the legacy components was demonstrated by the 28% increase in useful horizontal wind coverage as a result of the renovation. The new components were designed and installed by the company ATRAD.

The radar was entirely out of action from the morning of Monday 28th February 2011 until the afternoon of Monday 7th March. Thereafter, test operations were made each night and renovation work continued during the daytime. Although the radar was in good working order when the ATRAD team had completed the work on the afternoon of Friday 11th March, it stopped working at around 19:30 UT on Tuesday 15th March. This turned out to be caused, in part, by a communications problem between DAH's radar control software and the ATRAD beam steering control software. Once appropriate changes had been made to both, the radar successfully resumed operations at around 12:00 UT on Thursday 17th March.

In order to provide a reference dataset for evaluating the performance of the renovated radar, a special ST-mode observation format was used between 9th and 28th February 2011. This covered 16 of the 17 available beam pointing directions in a 9 minute 50 second long cycle of 24 dwells (a standard observation cycle covers 6 beam pointing directions in a 4 minute 55 second long cycle of 12 dwells). Owing to legacy hardware limitations, beam 12 (NE12.0) could not be accessed at this time. However, the post-renovation observations encompassed all 17 beam pointing directions in an 11 minute 40 second long cycle of 27 dwells. The new beam steering components have resulted in an increase in the gap between dwells from 3.6 to 4.9 s.

An immediate confirmation of the post-renovation beam pointing direction consistency was made by visual inspection of the spectral data plots. As expected, similar patterns were seen for beam pointing directions which shared the same azimuth angle, albeit with the Doppler shifts of the signals being scaled as a function of the (cosine of the) zenith angle. After several hours' worth of observations had been accumulated, the plots of the latest Cartesian data products could be used to verify that the wind data looked physically-realistic. After several days' worth of observations had been accumulated, it was possible to analyse the diurnal variations of spectral noise power. For each beam pointing direction, there should be a specific pattern which follows the variations in 46.5 MHz cosmic emissions along a circle of constant declination. Although the patterns for the pre and post renovation periods were qualitatively well-matched, there was an increase in the absolute values (i.e. in the system noise) by approximately 1 dB. Although the cause for this was never identified, the system noise actually decreased by approximately 1 dB compared to pre-renovation levels after changes were made to the radar control and beam steering software on 17th March - see above.

After several weeks' worth of observations had been accumulated, it was possible to carry out a statistical analysis of the Cartesian data products. Although the change in useful coverage for horizontal wind data (from 60.4% to 77.7%) was substantial, that for the vertical wind data (from 93.7% to 96.3%) was quite modest. This suggests that the old beam steering components were causing a large attenuation of the signals for off-vertical beam pointing directions but very little attenuation for the vertical

direction. This interpretation is consistent with changes seen in the the signal power decreases occurring between vertical beam and 6° off-vertical observations, i.e. the aspect sensitivity. The values are expected to be small throughout much of the troposphere, where isotropic scattering is a common radar return mechanism. Although, as might be expected, the peak of the distribution of post-renovation values occurred in the 1 - 2 dB range, it occurred in the 7 - 8 dB range immediately beforehand. The zenith angle dependence of radar scatter is expected to be larger in the lower-stratosphere, where non-isotropic scattering mechanisms predominate. Nevertheless, here too the location of the peak of the distribution was shifted (by 4 dB) to lower values post-renovation.

Non-isotropic scattering causes the effective zenith angle of a radar beam to be slightly smaller than its nominal value. Horizontal wind speeds must be compensated for this effect by applying a scaling factor, which is derived from the ratio of signal powers observed at 4.2° and 6.0° off-vertical - see e.g. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00585-997-0805-8>. A comparison of the pre and post renovation distributions of these values suggests that wind speeds were being over-compensated by around 6% during the pre-renovation period. This might explain, in part, why model-comparison statistics indicate improved 30-minute-averaged wind data quality for the post-renovation period - see section 4e. A decrease in the root mean square time differences between horizontal wind vectors suggests a reduction in random measurement errors for unaveraged wind data. Several more months' worth of observations will be required in order to unambiguously attribute these change to the effects of the renovation.

The new beam steering components will allow the number of available beam pointing directions to be increased from 17 to 255. However, there are no immediate plans to take advantage of this for the ST-mode. The current standard observation format, which makes use of only 6 of the current 17 directions, has proved to be well-optimised for addressing a broad range of scientific questions. Consequently it is ilikely to continue to be used almost-exclusively for the foreseeable future. Nevertheless, a few specific questions can only be addressed using pan-directional observations. For this reason, DAH deliberately extended their use in the post-renovation period from 3 weeks (to match the pre-renovation test period) to 7 weeks (ending on 3rd May 2011). The aim was to capture as broad a range of atmospheric conditions as possible.

Another reason to be cautious of adding new beam pointing directions is that the existing ones exhibit considerable variations in the quality of the ST-mode Doppler spectra (for both the pre and post renovation periods). In particular, beams 12 (NE12.0) and 14 (SE12.0) tend to be contaminated by secondary signals, which makes them unsuitable for wind-profiling purposes. The secondary signals are comparable in strength to the primary ones but bear little relationship in terms of Doppler velocities. It is thought that they are a result of unfavourable beam sidelobe patterns. Nevertheless, this might not be a problem for observations made with the intention of detecting objects in near-Earth orbits, i.e. at altitudes of a few hundred kilometres. This is a new area of research for which increased flexibility in the beam pointing direction will be an advantage.

3b) Electricity, including NERC's Voltage Optimisation scheme

NERC is conducting a programme of voltage optimisation for the electricity supplies to all of its sites. This involves reducing the mains voltage from 240 V to 220 V with the aim of decreasing power consumption - see minutes of the 46th meeting for further details. A voltage optimisation unit was being installed at the MST radar site on the day of the last Experimenters' meeting, i.e. on 15th February 2011. This required all equipment to be powered down between approximately 09:45 and 15:15 UT. However, the unit was installed in a part of the electrical circuit which only affected the supply to the transmitter room. Consequently everything had to be powered down again, between 08:00 and 14:45 UT on 7th April 2011, whilst the unit was moved to the correct position. NERC has been monitoring electricity consumption at all of its sites for over a year. Consequently it will eventually be in a position to evaluate the impact of the voltage optimisation units.

The units are designed to filter out transients in the incoming supply. Nevertheless, brief irregularities in their output voltages have been detected by the Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) units for the radar transmitters on two occasions: on 13th May and on 1st June 2011.

A Periodic Test And Inspection survey was carried out on the site's electricity infrastructure on Saturday 12th March 2011. No equipment had to be powered down. Everything was found to be in a good condition.

3c) Telecommunications

There have been a number of issues with the internet connections to the site over the past 6 months. It was reported at the 46th Experimenters' meeting that (download) line speeds for the NERC and Manchester networks had been very low (around 0.2 Mbit/s). This was caused by the inadvertent use of out-of-date Internet Service Provider (ISP) login details for the broadband modems. DPW had already adopted the new details for the Manchester modem at the time of the last meeting. This had resulted in the line speed increasing to around 2.5 Mbit/s. However, DAH had not been able to successfully change any of the settings on the NERC network's (Cisco 870) modem for over a year (it turns out that this was probably the result of the modem's internal software being incompatible with Windows Java updates). Consequently he installed a new modem (a D-link DSL-2740R) on 14th March 2011. However, even when using the new login details, the line speed was initially only 0.5 Mbit/s. When DAH spoke to the ISP on 12th April 2011, they discovered that the speed for the NERC line had been deliberately capped at some point in the past (presumably by BT). This is typically done as a way of maximising transfer reliability on a poor quality line. However, since the ISP could not find any records justifying the cap, they arranged to have it removed. By 14th April, line speeds had increased to 2.4 Mbit/s for downloads and 0.7 Mbit/s for uploads.

The D-link modem proved to be unsuitable for use at the MST radar site for two reasons. Firstly, it had limited Network Address Translation (NAT) capabilities. This meant that it was possible to set up connections to only two machines from outside of the LAN. Secondly, and more significantly, it could not maintain its broadband connection indefinitely. Three communications failures occurred within just three months. Although the connection could be re-established by simply power-cycling the unit, this required someone to be on site. The first instance occurred at around 23:20 UT on Friday 6th May 2011. This led to a 57 hour blockage of all data transfers before DPW arrived on site the following Monday morning (9th May). The second instance occurred at around 22:20 UT on Tuesday 7th June 2011 and led to a 10 hour blockage of transfers. The third instance occurred at around 21:20 UT on Friday 17th June 2011. DPW spotted (from home) that the latest MST radar data quick-look plots were not being updated. He came to the site on the following day specifically to restart the modem. This limited a potential 57 hour blockage to just 16 hours. DAH happened to be visiting site on 19th June 2011 and installed a replacement modem (a DrayTek 2830) at around 17:00 UT. This particular model had been recommended by one of DAH's RAL colleagues, who has networking expertise. It has so far operated without a fault.

A loss of broadband connection between 01:00 and 11:00 UT on Thursday 16th June 2011 (whilst the D-link modem was still in operation) turned out to be caused by a faulty telephone extension cable within the site. DPW was able to isolate the problem by listening for a dialling tone at various points along the circuit. Whilst he was doing this, the NERC modem was connected to the telephone line normally used for the Manchester network in order to clear the transfer backlog.

DK drew attention to the fact that if a dedicated LAN is used for the proposed Met Office ceilometer (see section 2), it would not be possible to directly access the data from the NERC LAN. He realised that this could be a problem during an observation campaign if someone required access to the data in real time. DAH pointed out that any webspace provided by the ISP could be used for showing quick-look plots of the latest data. By adopting this method for the NERC instruments, at

<http://www.mstrf.eclipse.co.uk/>, it is possible to avoid the delays which would be incurred by first sending the data to the BADC. DK suggested that it might be possible to give some people access to the latest plots from the Met Office's system. This is already done for WP data through the CWINDE system.

3d) Data management plan

GAP reported that, under the terms of NERC's recently-updated data policy, all data collected through NERC funding must eventually be made publicly available. Moreover, such data may be used for any purpose, including a commercial one. In general there can be an embargo period of up to 2 years before the data are released. This is to allow those responsible for collecting the data an exclusive chance to generate publications. However, routinely-collected data, such as are generated by the MST Radar Facility's instruments, should be made available as quickly as possible. Short delays for the purposes of carrying out quality control checks are permissible. In response to DAH's question, GV confirmed that MST radar collected during the forthcoming DIAMET and TROSIAD campaigns need not be subjected to an embargo period.

In connection with action item 44.4.2, GAP has been investigating a general BADC requirement to be able to differentiate between multiple versions of the same dataset. The files generated using the existing version of the MST radar signal processing software have a version number 3-2. Since the next version (see section 2) will incorporate a few minor bug fixes, the files will adopt version number 3-3.

DAH drew attention to the fact that he will need to create new versions of the laser ceilometer cloud base files dating back to 2nd November 2010. It turns out that the actual times are approximately 4 hours earlier than the recorded times in the files which are currently available through the BADC. This is the result of an unexpected reset of the instrument's internal clock. Owing to the known idiosyncracies of this clock - see minutes of the 46th meeting for further details - it has long been necessary to apply a software correction to the observation times. Until now, this has relied on hard-coding an offset time. However, given that all raw data for a UT day (as determined by the network time protocol enabled acquisition PC) are stored in a single file, it will be possible to determine the offset time dynamically. This would deal with the inevitable slow drift of the clock's time as well as with step changes of the type described above. GV pointed out that a timing error of 4 hours was unacceptable and that the corrupted files should be removed from the BADC as soon as possible.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.1 DAH and GAP to remove from public view, as soon as possible, those cloud base altitude files which have incorrect time stamps.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

NEW

3e) Miscellaneous

A test of the site's fire extinguishers was carried out by a member of Aberystwyth University staff during the last week of March 2011.

A Health and Safety (H&S) inspection of the site was carried out by a team from RAL on 10th May 2011. Their biggest concern was that the bungalow and the sheds were somewhat untidy and that there was a lot of "junk" lying around. DAH asked GV to ensure that large shed, which is used almost exclusively by the University of Manchester, is kept tidy and that any obsolete equipment is disposed of. The H&S team also drew attention to the fact that that the ruts left in the antenna field, as a result of the

recent radar renovation work, posed a trip hazard.

A TV crew from NHK, the Japanese equivalent of the BBC, visited the radar site on the afternoon of 19th June 2011. They were making a programme about noctilucent clouds (NLCs), which form around the mesopause level at upper-middle and high latitudes during the mid-summer months. They were interested in the related phenomenon of Mesosphere Summer Echoes (MSEs), which are observed by the MST radar. In preparation for this visit, DAH created a facility for automatically updating plots of the latest 24 hours' worth of M-mode data. This became active on 17th June 2011. The plots are available through the supplementary website.

Although the radar has been making continuous mesospheric observations since April 2005, only a single vertical beam dwell is used once every 5 minutes. Having read the following review paper in preparation for the NHK visit - <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/acp-4-2601-2004> - DAH decided that the scientific usefulness of the M-mode data could be considerably increased by adding observations in the NE6.0 and SE6.0 directions. These will allow both the zenith angle dependence of the scattering mechanism and the horizontal wind vector to be derived. The modifications to the standard observation format, which were introduced on 24th June 2011, will have a negligible effect on the ST-mode Cartesian data products. The new M-mode dwells replace two ST-mode vertical beam dwells, whose sole purpose was to make vertical velocity data continuously available at 51 s intervals. They were not used in the calculation of the horizontal wind data and there are still 4 ST-mode vertical beam dwells at 51 s intervals during the earlier part of the cycle. After 00:00 UT on 1st August 2011, the standard observation format will automatically revert to its earlier form, with a single M-mode vertical beam dwell once per cycle. Detectable mesospheric echoes are so rare outside of the mid-summer months that the additional observing time can be more-usefully devoted to ST-mode observations.

Before visiting Aberystwyth, the NHK TV crew had been to Anglesey to film John Rowlands, an amateur scientist who is carrying out an NLC-observing project in collaboration with Nick Mitchell from the University of Bath. DAH contacted John to let him know that the most impressive MSE of the season, in terms of persistence and vertical extent, had occurred on 2nd July 2011. It turns out that the NLC display on the night 2nd/3rd July "*was easily one of the most complex and brightest displays*" that John had seen. Pictures of NLCs for this and other nights during the 2011 season can be seen on John's NLC spotters' Facebook page - <http://www.facebook.com/pages/Noctilucent-Cloud-Observer-Network-2011/178014515556608>. CFL showed the meeting his own pictures of NLCs from the night of 2nd/3rd July, which he had taken during a trip to Scotland.

DAH reported that he hoped to use MSEs to test the potential for the MST radar to be operated in a bistatic mode with the LOFAR (radio-astronomy) receiving array at Chilbolton. This arises from a recent paper study carried out by RAL on behalf of the Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (DSTL). It looked at the potential of these two instruments in combination to detect objects in the near-Earth environment. Owing to the 200 km separation between the sites, LOFAR (which is more-steerable than the MST Radar) would need to make observations at no more than 5° elevation in order to observe the ST part of the atmosphere above Aberystwyth. Using MSEs would allow the LOFAR elevation angle to rise to a more-realistic 23°. Another useful test would be to try to detect the International Space Station using monostatic MST radar observations. Although the MST radar has a maximum unambiguous range of 96 km, an object at an altitude of 350 km would range-alias three times over down to 62 km.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There have been no problems with this instrument during the past 6 months.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

There have been no problems with this instrument during the past 6 months.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

There have been two periods when no data were recorded as a result of DAH forgetting to manually restart the acquisition software on PC "augustus" after it was rebooted. The first occurred between 09:37 UT on 15th February 2011 and 08:02 UT on the following day. "Augustus" had been powered down for the voltage optimisation work described in section 3b. The second occurred between 13:06 UT on 16th March 2011 and 08:13 UT on the following day. "Augustus" had been rebooted in an attempt to clear the problem which had stopped the radar working on 15th March - see section 3a.

There was an additional data gap of almost 48 hours, between 14:52 UT on 12th March 2011 and 10:36 on 14th March. "Augustus" had not been rebooted on this occasion but its connection to the instrument, at the back of the PC, was found to be loose. It is likely that the connection was disturbed during the Periodic Test And Inspection survey on the 12th March 2011 (see section 3b).

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

The instrument malfunctioned between 04:19 and 09:27 UT on 5th March 2011. The error code indicated, "*Test laser failure. Error. No more measurements possible*". This problem has previously been associated with extremely cold outside temperatures. However, on this occasion the minimum night-time temperature was only -3°C. The instrument began to function again without any intervention being taken. It was in connection with this problem that DAH first began to suspect that there was a timing problem with the data - see section 3d.

The backscatter data for the afternoon of 10th April 2011 show a cloud of what is thought to be Saharan dust. This does not show up in the cloud base altitude data, presumably because the range-squared-corrected backscatter power is too low to be interpreted as being associated with a regular cloud.

4e) Sky-camera

There have been no problems with this instrument during the past 6 months. DAH will supervise a work experience student at RAL on a sky-camera project between 11th and 15th July 2011. The student is required to methodically work through animations of the sky-camera images and to record the start and stop times of interesting phenomena. This will be the 5th student contributing to the sky-camera event log, which is made available through the Facility's website.

4f) MST Radar

The Met Office monthly model-comparison statistics do not suggest any issues with wind-profile data quality over the past 6 months. The information is given in graphical form, showing a number of statistical measures as functions of model level number. Since January 2011, the Met Office have also been sending out single number statistics, which are generated as part of the European E-WINPROF programme, which is part of the EUMETNET Composite Observing System (EUCOS) programme. The key parameter is labelled "Quality" and is described as the monthly root mean square difference OB-FG, presumably between the observed and first guess (i.e. model) winds at all times and levels. The EUCOS target is for this to be less than 5.0 m/s. The values - 5.3 m/s for January 2011, 5.3 m/s for February, 3.5 m/s for March and 3.9 m/s for April - suggest an improvement in data quality as a result of the radar renovation in early March 2011. The increased value of 6.2 m/s for May 2011 appears to be related to 2 instances of clearly-erroneous wind speeds within very narrow time and altitude regions. The first occurred within a single range gate, at an altitude of 10.935 km, between 22:30 and 23:00 UT on 22nd May. The second occurred at 3 consecutive range gates, with altitudes between 9.890 and 10.189 km,

between 06:00 and 06:30 UT on 29th May. The Met Office drew DAH's attention to both cases, for which the causes remain unknown. DAH is keen to gain greater access to such data as they clearly have value for identify signal processing limitations which are not otherwise apparent.

Another of the E-WINPROF parameters is labelled as "Timeliness". It represents the percentage of wind-profile messages which are received within 30 minutes of the end of the observation period. The EUCOS target is for a minimum of 90%. DAH had previously optimised the signal processing chain so that wind-profile messages are typically delivered to the Met Office within 20 minutes of the end of a 30 minute averaging period (see minutes of the 42nd meeting). Consequently there was no surprise at the timeliness values of 99% for January 2011, 99% for February, and 95% for May. This optimisation was based on a typical cycle length of around 5 minutes. DAH was therefore unsurprised at the low timeliness values of 62% for March 2011 and 66% for April, when the 11 minute 40 second long pan-directional observation format was in use.

It appears that the new beam steering controller is capable of providing diagnostic information which could be used for rapidly identifying hardware problems. One of the ATRAD engineers happened to log on to the unit on 22nd May 2011 and noticed that the forward power readings were unusually low for antenna sector A. This suggested that the corresponding transmitter, TX1, was down. Sure enough, when Les Dean (LD) visited the site on 24th May, he found that TX1 had blown a choke. It was back in operation later that morning.

The beam steering controller malfunctioned at 04:33 UT on 28th June. Amongst other things, this caused the beam pointing direction to remain in the vertical, resulting in erroneous wind-profile data being generated. DAH blocked the Met Office's data feed and stopped the radar shortly after 07:00 UT. LD happened to be on site that morning and changed phasing unit 77, which was flagged by the ATRAD software as being faulty. Nevertheless, the fault flag initially persisted, which lead LD to believe that a sub-optimal cable connection rather than an electronics fault was to blame. The fault flag cleared without LD having found any obvious problem. Operations resumed shortly after 09:30 UT. ATRAD later confirmed that the error status of phasing unit 77 had triggered the problem, which was then perpetuated by a communications issue between DAH's radar control and ATRAD's beam steering control software.

The radar commonly experiences interference, which (for the most part) can be effectively avoided by the signal processing software. DAH has long suspected that the interference was the result of overheating in part of the pre-processing or receiver circuits. Consequently LD had positioned a small fan to circulate air at the back of these units, albeit without any obvious effect. After having to temporarily remove the fan in early December 2010, when portable appliance testing was being carried out, LD re-attached it at the front of the units. No interference was observed from then until 21st May 2011, which suggests that this change had a beneficial effect. Nevertheless, interference was again seen on a large number of days in June 2011 (on 3rd, 4th, 10th, 11th, 13th, 14th, 15th, 16th, 22nd, 26th, 27th, 28th, and 29th) and on 2nd July 2011.

DAH fixed a long-standing but minor bug associated with the radar signal processing's time-continuity algorithm on 3rd May 2011. The data being flagged are compared with dwells which occur to either side in time. This is done separately for each beam pointing direction. A problem arose on the rare occasions when the radar observation format was changed and a particular beam pointing direction ceased to be used. The dwells ceased to move through the processing chain as intended - see e.g. minutes of the 39th meeting. The easiest way to avoid this problem was for DAH to manually flush out data for the discontinued beam pointing directions after a format change. Given that he would be faced with doing this 11 times when reverting from the pan-directional to standard observation format (see section 3a), it was more time-effective to fix the problem with the algorithm.

DAH reported that the MST radar data product files available through the BADC had initially been incomplete for 6th and 9th May 2011 and for 7th and 17th June 2011. This was a result of broadband

modem malfunctions (see section 3c), which also prevented data transfers taking place within the LAN. DAH had recreated the products files off-line and, in keeping with the new data management plan (see section 3d), these were only transferred to the BADC once it had been established that no-one had accessed the original files.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments - GV

GV reported that the FGAM BLWP now takes part in Met Office activities through an official collaboration with the Upper Air Network group. It was continuously operated at Cardington between April 2010 and June 2011 in support of the Future Upper-air Network Development (FUND) campaign. The wind data are now automatically sent to the Met Office irrespective of where the instrument is being operated. CG and DK clarified that the data are simply monitored. There is currently no effective way of operationally assimilating data from non-permanent instruments. During February 2011, a wind intercomparison was undertaken through a COST action. The BLWP was operated alongside a number of Doppler lidars: a Windcube, a Leosphere, and a Halo Photonics. The testing and development of algorithms for deriving boundary layer heights, from BLWP observations, is also taking place through a COST action. All raw data collected by the instrument since 2002 have now been transferred to the BADC.

The BLWP will be deployed to the MST Radar site between August and December 2011 in support of the DIAMET campaign - see section 6a. Thereafter it will return to Cardington in support of the ClearFlo campaign, which will have two phases. The first will be during January and February 2012. The second, during July and August 2012, is designed to coincide with the London Olympics. Emily Norton will start maternity leave in October 2011 and so GV requires someone at Cardington to oversee the instrument. For the most part DPW can run and monitor it remotely. However, it is occasionally necessary to have someone physically present. If the Convective Precipitation Experiment (COPE) is funded, the BLWP will be redeployed to either the MST radar site or Exeter during the latter part of 2012.

The BLWP has been aligned with north using a magnetic compass and without taking the offset from true north into account (the latter is currently around 3° for Cardington). Unsurprisingly, the Met Office monthly model-comparison statistics indicate a wind direction bias of a few degrees. It is planned to assimilate the data into the Unified Model (UM) once this offset has been corrected. DAH pointed out that LD had avoided this problem by using a GPS-based smart phone compass application when aligning the antenna for the new lightning detector. CFL added that, irrespective of the method used to determine north, the visual method of aligning the BLWP was only accurate to within a few degrees.

The BLWP was sent back to France, between May and August 2011, for a refurbishment. This involved the replacement of a number of components, including the antennas and the cables. The mechanical structure has also been reconditioned.

5b) University of Manchester instruments - GV

The static instruments will be used to support the TROSIAD campaign (see section 6a) later in 2011. The Elight lidar detected ash from the Grimsvötn eruption in Iceland during one brief event in 2011. GV offered to make the data available to anyone who might be interested. A post-doc will soon complete the analysis of the 2010 Eyjafjallajökull volcanic ash observations. The Leosphere lidar, which stopped working in 2010 after it was deployed to the Shetlands to track volcanic ash, has finally been returned from the manufacturers.

5c) Met Office GPS receiver

Jon Jones, who was not at the meeting, had reported to DAH that the PC for the Met Office's GPS water vapour receiver had been giving problems for some time. He (Jon) will need to visit the site in order to

investigate this further.

5d) Lightning detector

DAH reported that a lightning detector had been installed at the MST radar site in April 2011. It augments the existing pan-European network operated by the German company Nowcast. GV had arranged to have the instrument hosted in exchange for access to the lightning data, which will be useful for the TROSIAD campaign. However, it is only possible to access the very latest data, which restricts the usefulness. In response to GV's enquiry, MC confirmed that the Met Office do archive their own lightning data. GAP pointed out that the BADC used to archive such data but have not been able to do so since changes were made to the Met Office's system.

ACTION ITEM 47.5.1 GAP to ensure that the BADC archive Met Office lightning data to cover the TROSIAD campaign period.

NEW

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Diabatic Influences on Mesoscale Structures in Extra-Tropical Storms (DIAMET) - GV

In the forthcoming months there will be two windows of opportunity for FAAM flights in connection with this project. The first, between 14th and 30th September 2011 (excluding weekends), is when the aircraft will be based at Cranfield. The second, between 24th November and 15th December 2011 (including weekends), is when it will be based at Exeter. The plan is to deploy dropsondes from the aircraft as it flies over the sea. The Met Office will be launching campaign-dedicated radiosondes from their own sites. The TROSIAD campaign will be conducted in parallel with DIAMET and has the provision for launching radiosondes from the MST radar site. GV confirmed that the standard (300 m resolution) MST radar observation format would be appropriate. There will be an additional campaign phase in July/August 2012.

6b) Is tropopause folding promoting or suppressing deep convection? - BA

It has long been known that that stratospheric intrusions can promote deep convection, e.g. in the case study of 23rd - 24th May 2006. However, it has also become apparent that stratospheric intrusions can sometimes inhibit convection, e.g. in the case study of 1st - 2nd December 2006. The aim of the TROPOPAUSE folding Stratospheric Intrusion And Deep convection project (TROSIAD) is to clarify their overall impact. Initial work has focused on creating a climatology for the 2007 year.

ECMWF analysis cross-sections have been generated for instances of stratospheric intrusions which have been identified using MST radar data. 55% of the 64 cases for 2007 occurred during the winter months, i.e. December - March. Convective events have been identified from instances of intense rainfall in Nimrod data. 43% of the instances in the December - February months were associated with tropopause folds. The next step is to extend the climatology to cover the period 2006 - 2010.

BA has not yet started to consider the mechanisms responsible for triggering the convection. GV pointed out that coastal and orographic effects could play a role. DAH draw attention to the fact that it is possible to identify convective activity using MST radar data. GV clarified that since the MST radar only sees the conditions directly overhead, it could easily miss convective activity which was occurring nearby. Consequently the Nimrod data are more reliable for identifying convective conditions.

6c) Use of wind profilers to quantify atmospheric turbulence- CFL

The motivations behind this work are the need for quantitative turbulence information and its scarcity for altitudes above the surface layer. The spectral width of wind profiler (WP) signals appears to offer such information on a continuous basis and over a range of altitudes. However, CFL knows of only 2 previous studies which have attempted to calibrate such data against in situ measurements. Moreover,

as he has found out, owing to the fundamental differences in the measurement techniques, the procedure for intercomparing such data is far from straight-forward. CFL has analysed *in situ* measurements from 3 dedicated aircraft campaigns, for which coincident MST radar and (FGAM) BLWP observations are available. He has also analysed *in situ* measurements made from the tethered balloon at Cardington, for which coincident BLWP observations are available.

Unlike *in situ* probes, which make instantaneous point measurements, WPs sample a large volume of the atmosphere over a typical time period of tens of seconds. Consequently it is necessary to correct the observed WP spectral widths for a number of effects. CFL has found that applying a Gaussian fit to the WP signals is the best way to determine the spectral widths. He has noticed that the BLWP spectral widths increase as the limits of the observed spectrum increase, i.e. as the spectral resolution decreases. Since the instrument auto-adjusts the spectral parameters in order to cope with the anticipated range of conditions, the user has no control over this. CFL has considered whether this broadening might be caused a change in the data weighting window (used to derive the spectra) or in the degree of spectral smoothing applied. However, neither can explain it and the cause remains a mystery.

Following a suggestion made by Jeremy Price, CFL has looked at the effect of increasing the time scales over which aircraft data are analysed. This has the effect of incorporating larger turbulence scale sizes. As expected, the variance increases. However, WP spectral widths remain fairly constant as the sampling period is varied. CFL thinks that this is because the large observation volumes used by WPs automatically encompass a broad range of scale sizes, irrespective of the duration.

With all of the above factors taken into consideration, CFL has found good agreement between aircraft measurements and BLWP spectral widths derived from 75 m resolution observations. The 150 m resolution observations appear to be too coarse. He has also found that the assumed MST radar σ_0 beam width of 0.9° leads to an overcorrection of observed spectral widths for beam broadening. He achieved a better fit using a value of 0.8° .

CG suggested that a further intercomparison could be made between BLWP and Halo Doppler lidar data. DK pointed out that the lidar has a very small observation volume and so the intercomparison would encounter the same problems as when considering aircraft data. DK made the general comment that the hidden nature of the processing algorithms used by commercially-available WPs made it difficult to rely on the interpretation of some of the data products.

6d) An update on EG-CLIMET - CG

CG reported on the EG-CLIMET meeting which she had recently attended in Lindenberg. She is a member of the working group which looks at networks of integrated instruments. Chilbolton and Cabauw (in The Netherlands) are the two supersites for this project. On the instrumentation side, they are interested in how to improve data quality. For example, they are looking at the effects of convection on WP data.

A comparison of Halo and Windcube Doppler lidar observations was carried out at Cardington between February and April 2011. Use was also made of BLWP and radiosonde data. The spring of 2011 was a dry one and the lack of rain meant that there were high levels of aerosol. Lidar coverage consequently extended to 3 km. Both lidars show small biases in their wind measurements. These were slightly larger for the Halo lidar (which has an integration time of 30 s) than for the Windcube lidar (which has an integration time of 10 minutes). The Windcube lidar is small, has no frequency allocation issues, and can be set up in less than 10 minutes. These attractive characteristics make it an instrument worthy of further investigation.

At present internal Met Office data users primarily make use of the high (altitude coverage) mode data from the BLWPs. DK would like to see more use made of the low mode data, which provide better altitude resolution for the BL. However, the software used to deal with BLWP data has been adapted

from that originally written for radiosondes. Consequently it does not have the capacity to deal with the low mode data.

6e) Detailed Wind Profiler statistics- DK

WP model-comparison statistics, which are used for quality monitoring purposes, do not distinguish between the relative importance of uncertainties in wind speed and in wind direction. For this reason, DK and CG have been examining WP data in greater detail. Attention has been focused on 1 year's worth of data, from May 2010 to April 2011, from the Wattisham BLWP. There is evidence for different predominant wind characteristics at different altitudes. At range gate 2, which is at 352 m above mean sea level (amsl), there are two distinct clusters of winds (with similar speeds) in the SW and NE quadrants. At range gate 5, 577 m amsl, there is a broader spread of directions. At range gate 18, 1551 m amsl, there is a cluster in the NE quadrant but no longer one in the SW.

This type of analysis will be extended to cover selected WP sites. The generation of statistics and the visualisation of the results will be based on existing software. If these prove to be of use, an operational assessment process will be set up.

7. Any Other Business

The date for the next Experimenters' meeting was provisionally set for Tuesday 24th January 2012.